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New Records of Two Darwin Wasps (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae: Ophioninae and Pimplinae) from Lanyu, Taiwan Expand Their Distributional Ranges Northwards

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Abstract: Two new records of Darwin wasps (Ichneumonidae), *Leptophion vechti* Gauld & Mitchell, 1981 (Ophioninae) and *Lissopimpla basalis* (Vollenhoven, 1879) (Pimplinae), are first reported from Lanyu island, Taiwan. This extends the known northernmost distribution of both species and is the new northernmost record of the genus *Lissopimpla* Kriechbaumer. A redescription of *L. vechti* and a revised key to Taiwanese *Leptophion* are provided.

Key words: identification key, *Leptophion*, *Lissopimpla*, biogeography, faunistics

Introduction

Lanyu island, also known as Botel Tobago island, Koto-sho island, or Orchid island, is a small volcanic island located southeast of the main island of Taiwan. Lanyu island shares fauna and flora with both the Taiwanese main island and the Philippines, despite its considerably greater distance from the Philippines compared to Taiwan (Kano, 1933, 1936a, 1936b, 1941; Li, 1953; Chang, 1986; Hsu & Wolf, 2009). Japanese naturalist Tadao Kano (1906–?) therefore suggested a northern extension of the hypothetical biogeographical line known as the “Merrill-Dickerson line”, a line originally placed between Borneo and Sulawesi and extending northward between Borneo and Palawan (Dikerson et al., 1928; Van Welzen et al., 2011). Kano referred to this extended boundary as the “Neo-Wallace Line”, positioning it between the Taiwanese main island and Lanyu island based on his observations of regional geology, climate, and biota (Kano, 1933, 1936a, 1936b, 1941).

Previous insect faunistic studies on Lanyu island have primarily focused on Lepidoptera and Coleoptera (e.g., Fukuda & Hashimoto, 1975; Starr & Wang, 1992; Liu et al., 2021). The frequent discovery of new taxa highlights the island's high endemism and unique biogeographical characteristics (e.g., Yen et al., 2003; Hsu & Huang, 2008; Chen et al., 2017; Lee & Konstantinov, 2024). However, the knowledge of the Hymenoptera fauna of Lanyu, particularly the Darwin wasps (Ichneumonidae), one of the most diverse families within this order (Broad et al. 2018), is scarce (e.g., Uchida, 1937).

Fifteen species of Darwin wasps have been recorded from Lanyu island, as summarized in Table 1. Among them, four species or subspecies have been recorded only from Lanyu island in Taiwan, with others also distributed on the main island of Taiwan (Table 1) (Chiu et al., 1984). We recognized two Darwin wasp species from Lanyu island that do not match the 15 species previously recorded and we here identify and report those findings.

Materials and methods

General morphological terms follow Broad et al. (2018), and the measurements and abbreviations used for Ophioninae mainly follow Shimizu et al. (2016) and listed below:

Head: **OD** = posterior ocellar diameter; **POL** = distance between posterior ocelli; **OOL** = minimum distance between posterior ocellus and eye; **FI** (frontal index) = median ocellar diameter / minimum distance between eyes in anterior view; lower face = the area from the lower margin of the clypeus to the lower margin of the antennal sockets, specifically used in Ophioninae (Gauld & Mitchell, 1981).

Fore wing: **AI** (alar index) = length of 1m-cu&M between 2m-cu and bulla / length of 3rs-m; **CI** (cubital index) = length of CU in postnervulus / length of 2cu-a in postnervulus; **DI** (discoidal index) = maximum vertical height of second discal cell / length of CU in posterior second discal cell; **ICI** (intercubital index) = length of 3rs-m / length of M between 2m-cu and 3rs-m; **SDI** (second discoidal index) = length of CU in posterior second discal cell / length of CU in posterior discosubmarginal cell.

Hind wing: **NI** (nervellar index) = length of CU in nervellus / length of cu-a.

Metasoma: **T** = tergite; **DMI** (dorsal metasomal index) = length of T2 in lateral view / length of T3 in lateral view; **PI** (petiolar index) = length of T1 between its base and anterior margin of spiracle in lateral view / length of T1 between posterior margin of spiracle and its apex in lateral view.

Live photos were taken using a CANON EOS 700D camera equipped with a CANON EF100mm F2.8L MACRO IS USM lens. Specimens were examined and measured using a LEICA S8APO microscope (Leica Microsystems, Germany) and an electronic micrometer (TEKFAR Inc., Taichung, Taiwan). Measurements connected by an en dash represent the minimum and maximum values; values in parentheses with a plus-minus sign indicate the mean and standard deviation; and values in brackets represent the measurements of the holotype as given in the original description. Photographs of specimens were taken with a LEICA DMC5400 camera and LEICA Z16 APO lens then processed using the LAS V4.13 auto-stacking system (Leica Microsystems). All figures were edited and arranged into plates using Adobe Illustrator CC and Photoshop CC (Adobe Systems Inc., San Jose, CA, USA).

Voucher specimens from this study are deposited in the National Museum of Natural Science, Taichung, Taiwan (NMNS) and Taiwan Agricultural Research Institute, Taichung, Taiwan (TARI). The abbreviations for type depositions in the synonymy list is presented as follows: Nationaal Natuurhistorisch Museum Naturalis, Leiden, Netherland (RMNH); Institut Royal des Sciences Naturelles de Belgique, Belgium (IRSNB).

Table 1. Checklist of Darwin wasps from Lanyu island before this study, listed in alphabetical order of Latin names. Abbreviations: **LY**, Lanyu island; **TW**, main island of Taiwan.

Current status	Distribution in Taiwanese islands	References	Remarks
<i>Agrypon sulcosus</i> Uchida, 1937	LY	Uchida, 1937: 12; Chiu et al., 1984: 39	Recorded as <i>Camposcopus sulcosus</i> Uchida, 1937 in Chiu et al. (1984)
<i>Algathia kurarensis</i> (Uchida, 1927)	TW, LY	Uchida, 1937: 9; Chiu et al., 1984: 44	Recorded as <i>Vulgichneumon kurarensis</i> (Uchida, 1927) in Uchida (1937) and Chiu et al. (1984)
<i>Apophua kikuchii</i> (Uchida, 1932)	TW, LY	Chiu, 1965: 216	Recorded as <i>Glypta (Apophua) kikuchii</i> (Uchida, 1932) in Uchida (1937)
<i>Colpotrochia pilosa pilosa</i> Cameron, 1909	TW, LY	Chiu, 1962: 20	
<i>Enicospilus pungens</i> (Smith, 1874)	TW, LY	Uchida, 1937: 11; Chiu, 1954: 25; Chiu et al., 1984: 32	Recorded as synonyms, <i>Henicospilus lineolatus</i> Roman, 1913, <i>E. uniformis</i> Chiu, 1954, and <i>E. lineolatus</i> (Roman)
<i>Goryphus hyalinoides</i> (Uchida, 1937)	TW, LY	Uchida, 1937: 9; Chiu et al., 1984: 18	Recorded as <i>Goryphus opacus</i> (Smith, 1859) in Uchida (1937)
<i>Hypsicera femoralis</i> (Geoffroy, 1785)	TW, LY	Chiu, 1962: 30	
<i>Metopius rufus browni</i> Ashmead, 1905	TW, LY	Chiu, 1962: 6	
<i>Nipponaetes haeussleri</i> (Uchida, 1933)	TW, LY	Chen & Shiao, 2024: 14	
<i>Nipponaetes striatus</i> Momoi, 1970	TW, LY	Chen & Shiao, 2024: 17	
<i>Teleutaea gracilis</i> Cushman, 1933	TW, LY	Chiu, 1965: 207	
<i>Torbda striata</i> Uchida, 1956	LY	Chiu et al., 1984: 21	
<i>Triancyra kanoi</i> (Uchida, 1937)	LY	Uchida, 1937: 10; Chiu et al., 1984: 9	Recorded as <i>Epirhyssa kanoi</i> in Uchida (1937)
<i>Xanthopimpla ochracea yami</i> Uchida, 1937	LY	Uchida, 1937: 10; Townes and Chiu, 1970: 131	Recorded as <i>Xanthopimpla kriegeri</i> f. <i>yami</i> in Uchida (1937)
<i>Xanthopimpla punctata</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	TW, LY	Townes and Chiu, 1970: 222	

Results

New records of Darwin wasps on Lanyu island

The two Darwin wasps collected from Lanyu island were identified as *Leptophion vechti* Gauld & Mitchell, 1981 (Ophioninae) and *Lissopimpla basalis* (Vollenhoven, 1879) (Pimplinae). Both represent not only the first records from this island but also northernmost range extensions for each species. The female of *Leptophion vechti* is described here for the first time (see Taxonomy section). Chinese vernacular names for both species are proposed to facilitate better information exchange among citizen scientists in Taiwan.

Taxonomy

Order Hymenoptera Linnaeus, 1758
Family Ichneumonidae Latreille, 1802
Subfamily Ophioninae Shuckard, 1840
Genus *Leptophion* Cameron, 1901
細瘦姬蜂屬

Chinese vernacular name. The Chinese vernacular name was first proposed by Chao (1976). The term “細 (slender)” corresponds to the Greek prefix “*Lepto-*,” meaning “thin, fine, narrow, or slender.” “瘦姬蜂” is the Chinese common name for the subfamily Ophioninae, referring to its slender body shape.

Diagnosis. See Shimizu et al. (2016).

***Leptophion vechti* Gauld & Mitchell, 1981**
威赫特細瘦姬蜂
(Figs 1, 3A, B)

Leptophion vechti Gauld & Mitchell, 1981: 71. Holotype: ♂, Sumatra, Indonesia (RMNH).

Diagnosis. According to Gauld & Mitchell (1981), this species can be separated from other congeners by the following combination of characters: fore wing 2r&RS joining base to middle of pterostigma (Fig. 1F); hind tarsal claw with pectens projected beyond apex of the claw (Fig. 1H); hind wing with 5 or more uniform distal hamuli (Fig. 1G); hind wing with first abscissa of RS slightly curved, proximal corner of marginal cell about 60–70° (Fig. 1F); lateral carina of scutellum present and extend behind anterior half (Figs 1D, 3A); fore wing with 1m-cu&M strongly sinuous with vestigial ramulus (Figs 1F, 3A).

Material examined. Non-type materials. TAIWAN • Taitung County, Lanyu Township (Lanyu island) • 1♂3♀♀, Datianchi [大天池], 08. V. 2021, Cheng-Han Ma leg., sweeping, sample ID: CHP00726–729, voucher: NMNS ENT 8951-11–14; 1♂, Lanan, 26–27. IV. 1997, M. L. Chan & H. T. Chan leg., mercury light, voucher: NMNS ENT 1667-2393; 1♂, Chingching Grasses [青青草原], 28–29. IV. 1997, M. L. Chan & M. M. Yang leg., UV light, voucher: NMNS ENT 2667-1606.

Redescription based on Lanyu specimens.**Female (n=3)**

Head (Figs 1B, C, E) polished and entirely punctate with setae, $1.67\text{--}2.00 \times (1.82 \pm 0.17)$ as wide as long; occipital carina complete; lower face $0.79\text{--}0.81 (0.80 \pm 0.01)$ \times as wide as high; clypeus polished and sparsely punctate with setae, $1.79\text{--}2.53 \times (2.08 \pm 0.40)$ as wide as high, with ventral margin rounded; FI = $0.56\text{--}0.63 (0.59 \pm 0.03)$; OD = $0.38\text{--}0.42 (0.40 \pm 0.02)$ mm, POL/OD = $0.29\text{--}0.42 (0.35 \pm 0.07)$, OOL/OD = $0.05\text{--}0.08 (0.06 \pm 0.02)$; mandibles equally bidentate and parallele, twisted with both teeth visible in anterior view; flagellum with at least 52 segments (all examined specimens with antennae broken apically); first flagellomere $7.50\text{--}8.50 \times (7.98 \pm 0.50)$ as long as wide, $1.75\text{--}2.29 \times (2.08 \pm 0.29)$ as long as second flagellomere.

Mesosoma (Figs 1A, D, E) polished and entirely punctate with setae; mesoscutum $1.42\text{--}1.53 \times (1.49 \pm 0.06)$ as long as wide, with notauli absent; scutellum with lateral carina present on anterior $0.80\text{--}0.85 (0.82 \pm 0.02)$; epinomial carina about $0.5 \times$ as high as mesopleuron, curved ventrally; metapleuron and propodeum with submetapleural carina, pleural carina, and anterior transverse carina strong and complete, median longitudinal carina short and present medially behind anterior transverse carina, other carinae absent; dorsal surface of propodeum with irregular strong rugae behind anterior transverse carina; lateral profile of propodeum straightly sloped behind anterior transverse carina.

Wings (Figs 1F, G) with fore wing $12.14\text{--}13.34 (12.64 \pm 0.63)$ mm; AI = $0.98\text{--}1.07 (1.01 \pm 0.05)$; CI = $0.31\text{--}0.37 (0.34 \pm 0.03)$; DI = $0.45\text{--}0.56 (0.51 \pm 0.06)$; ICI = $0.86\text{--}0.96 (0.91 \pm 0.05)$; SDI = $0.68\text{--}0.69 (0.69)$; 1m-cu&M sinuous, with vestigial ramulus; proximal 0.5 of 2r&RS straight and broadened, curved at midpoint and straight and normal distally; discosubmarginal cell with glabrous area below pterostigma; distoposterior corner of second distal cell about 90–95°. Hind wing $8.70\text{--}8.75 (8.72 \pm 0.03)$ mm; NI = $1.15\text{--}1.43 (1.29 \pm 0.14)$; RS slightly curved proximally; marginal cell setose, except proximal area with linear setal band surrounded by glabrous area; proximal corner of marginal cell about 70°; distal hamuli 5–6, uniform in shape.

Legs (Figs 1A, H) with hind femur $0.72\text{--}0.76 \times (0.75 \pm 0.02)$ as long as hind tibia; first hind tarsomere $1.96\text{--}2.05 \times (1.99 \pm 0.05)$ as long as second hind tarsomere, $0.45\text{--}0.47 \times (0.46 \pm 0.01)$ as long as hind tibia; second hind tarsomere $1.65\text{--}1.71 \times (1.68 \pm 0.05)$ as long as third hind tarsomere; hind tarsal claw with pectens extend beyond true apex of claw.

Metasoma (Figs 1A) polished with setae; T1 $5.11\text{--}5.57 \times (5.27 \pm 0.26)$ as long as its posterior width, PI = 2.07–2.18 (2.12 ± 0.06); DMI = 1.15–1.26 (1.20 ± 0.06); ovipositor sheath $0.37\text{--}0.40 \times (0.39 \pm 0.01)$ as long as hind tibia.

Coloration (Fig. 1) generally yellowish brown; lower face, clypeus, temple, approximately dorsal half of gena, vertex, dorsal surface of pronotum, scutellum yellowish white; longitudinal stripes on lateral lobes of mesoscutum, sometimes median lobe blackish brown; metasoma brown posteriorly. Wings hyaline, with veins and pterostigma blackish brown; proximal area of fore wing marginal cell, distal corner of discosubmarginal cell, and proximal area of second subdiscal cell weakly infumate.

Male (n=1)

Similar to female, with following measurements: head $1.81 \times$ as wide as long, lower face $0.84 \times [0.85]$ as wide as high, clypeus $2.00 \times$ as wide as high, OD 0.44 mm, POL/OD = 0.32, OOL/OD = 0.02, FI = 0.68, flagellum broken at least with 45 segments, first flagellomere $7.06 \times$ as long as wide, $1.94 \times [1.90]$ as long as second flagellomere; mesoscutum $1.40 \times$ as long as wide, scutellum with lateral carina present in anterior $0.84 [0.7]$; fore wing 12.50 [13.0] mm, AI = 1.02 [1.10], CI = 0.31 [0.18], DI = 0.52, ICI = 0.83 [0.69], SDI = 0.63 [0.82]; hind wing length 8.60 mm, NI = 1.07 [0.92], distal hamuli 5 [5], proximal corner of marginal cell about $70^\circ [60^\circ]$; legs with hind femur $0.77 \times$ as long as hind tibia, first hind tarsomere $1.93 \times$ as long as second hind tarsomere, $0.50 \times$ as long as hind tibia, second hind tarsomere $1.77 \times$ as long as third hind tarsomere; metasoma with T1 $4.94 \times$ as long as its posterior width, PI = 2.36; DMI = 1.11.

Chinese vernacular name. The Chinese vernacular name is first proposed here. “威赫特” is a Mandarin transliteration of the surname “Vecht,” serving as the eponym (the collector of the holotype J. van der Vecht) for the specific name “*vechti*.”

Distribution. Indonesia (Sumatra, type locality) (Gauld & Mitchell, 1981) and Taiwan (Lanyu, new record).

Remarks.

The record of this species from Lanyu island, Taiwan, is the first from outside its type locality in Sumatra, Indonesia. This finding extends the known northernmost distribution of the species.

Based on the first morphological comparison between female and male specimens of this species, we confirm that it lacks significant sexual dimorphism, as is the case with many other species in the subfamily Ophioninae. A live photo (Fig. 3B) shows individuals gathering and resting on the underside of evergreen leaves, which may be a common behavior in *Leptophion*, as suggested by numerous records from citizen scientists on Facebook (e.g., <https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=9924979360851215>, <https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=4872272786128928>, <https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=3279354715614519>). Combining observations from online sources (January to March for *L. maculipennis* and *L. giganteus*) and this study (May for *L. vechti*), aggregations were observed during seasons when the target species are commonly found (Shimizu et al., 2016), suggesting that this behavior may not be seasonal but rather represents a form of diurnal resting in *Leptophion*.

Key to Taiwanese species of the genus *Leptophion*.

The key to Taiwanese species of *Leptophion* proposed by Shimizu et al. (2016) is revised here by including *L. vechti*. The Chinese vernacular names of three other Taiwanese species (*L. giganteus* Shimizu & Watanabe, 2016, *L. maculipennis* (Cameron, 1905), and *L. radiatus* (Uchida, 1956)) are also proposed here.

1. Hind wing with non-uniform hamuli, penultimate hamulus significantly elongated; proximoposterior part of second subdiscal cell of fore wing entirely hyaline without infumate area; proximal corner of marginal cell of hind wing about 95° ; known from lowland to high-elevation area of Taiwan.....*L. maculipennis* (Cameron, 1905) [斑翅細瘦姬蜂]
- Hind wing with uniform hamuli, penultimate hamulus not elongated; proximoposterior part of second subdiscal cell of fore wing with weak to distinct infumate area; proximal corner of marginal cell of hind wing about $45\text{--}75^\circ$2
2. Lateral carina of scutellum present on anterior $0.8\text{--}0.9$ (Figs 1D, 3A); fore wing 1m-cu&M sinuous with vestigial ramulus (Figs 1F, 3A); proximal corner of marginal cell of hind wing about $60\text{--}70^\circ$ (Fig. 1F); known from Lanyu island.....*L. vechti* Gauld & Mitchell, 1981 [威赫特細瘦姬蜂*]

- Lateral carina of scutellum present on anterior 0.2; fore wing 1m-cu&M sinuous or straight, without vestigial ramulus; proximal corner of marginal cell of hind wing about 45°; known from main island of Taiwan.....3
- 3. Fore wing 1m-cu&M strongly sinuous; distoposterior corner of second discal cell of fore wing forming obtuse angle about 105–110°; fore wing with AI = 1.1–1.4, ICI=0.9–1.0, SDI=1.1–1.2; fore wing weakly infumate except proximal part of marginal cell often with distinct infumate area (but occasionally no more infumate than apex of cell), and proximoposterior part of second subdiscal cell with distinct infumate area; fore wing 17.0–21.0 mm; known from mid-elevation area of Taiwan *L. giganteus* Shimizu & Watanabe, 2016 [巨細瘦姬蜂*]
- Fore wing 1m-cu&M straight; distoposterior corner of second discal cell of fore wing forming acute angle about 85°; fore wing with AI = 0.8–0.9, ICI=0.5–0.7, SDI=0.9–1.0; fore wing hyaline except for proximal part of marginal cell and proximoposterior corner of second subdiscal cell each with infumate area; fore wing 13.0–15.0 mm; known from mid- to high-elevation area of Taiwan..... *L. radiatus* (Uchida, 1956) [直脈細瘦姬蜂*]

* An asterisk indicates a newly-proposed Chinese vernacular name.

Subfamily Pimplinae Wesmeal, 1845
Genus *Lissopimpla* Kriechbaumer, 1889
 麗瘤姬蜂屬

Chinese vernacular name. The Chinese vernacular name is proposed here for the first time. “麗 (beautiful)” is a Mandarin transliteration of the Greek prefix “*Lisso-*,” meaning “smooth,” which refers to the smooth metasomal tergites characteristic of this genus. “瘤姬蜂” is the common Chinese name for the subfamily Pimplinae, highlighting the elevated areas on the metasomal tergites typical of this group. The name “麗瘤姬蜂” is also refer to the distinctive and beautiful color pattern usually observed from the species of this genus. Notably, a more accurate translation, “光瘤姬蜂” (meaning “polished pimpline wasp”), is already used for the pimpline genus *Liotryphon* Ashmead, 1900.

Diagnosis. According to Gauld (1984), this genus can be separated from other pimpline congeners by the following combination of characters: clypeus divided into dorsal and ventral parts by a transverse suture (Figs 2C, F); face with distinct vertical impressions either side of raised median longitudinal carina (Figs 2C, F); mandibles strongly narrowed and twisted (Figs 2C, F); occipital carina complete; epicnemial carinae present (Fig. 2H); mesopleuron with median impressed groove (Fig. 2H); propodeum transversely carinate with apophyses (Fig. 2G); fore wing with 3rs-m present, forming areolet (Figs 2E); hind wing nervellus with first abscissa of CU extremely short, base of second abscissa of CU almost joining M; metasomal tergites polished and smooth (Fig. 2G).

***Lissopimpla basalis* (Vollenhoven, 1879)**
 黑基麗瘤姬蜂
 (Figs 2, 3C)

Pimpla basalis Vollenhoven, 1879: 148. Holotype: ♂, Sumatra, Indonesia (RMNH).

Trichrus stupenda Tosquinet, 1903: 374. Syntypes: ♂♀, Java, Indonesia (IRSNB). Synonymized by Townes et al. (1961: 47).

Diagnosis. This species can be separated from congeners by the following combination of characters: median transverse groove on mesopleuron weak and not trans-striate posteriorly (Fig. 2H); fore wing 1cu-a far basad to M&RS (Figs 2B); metasomal T1–2 black with reddish band posteriorly and yellowish at latero-posterior corners (female), or yellowish band posteriorly (male) (Figs 2A, B, D, E); metasomal tergites after T4 reddish brown, tinged with black dorso-anteriorly (Figs 2A, B, D, E); all legs reddish brown (Figs 2A, B, D, E); mesosoma black, with single spot on median lobe of mesoscutum, scutellum, ventral half of mesopleuron, and apophyses of propodeum yellowish (Figs 2A, B, D, E, G, H).

Material examined. Non-type materials. TAIWAN • Taitung County, Lanyu Township (Lanyu island) • 1♂, Tianchr [天池] NO.1, 26. IX.–10. X. 1998, H. T. Shih leg., Malaise trap, sample ID: 19981010LT1MAHYM010, voucher: NMNS ENT 3209-887; 1♂, Yonghsing [永興] NO.1, 1–20. IX. 1998, H. T. Shih leg., Malaise trap, voucher: NMNS ENT 3209-677; 1♀, Tianchr NO.2, 18. VIII. 1998, H. T. Shih leg., Malaise trap, sample ID: 19980818LT2MAHYM004, voucher: NMNS ENT 3209-222; 1♂, Yunghsing LY2, 14–17. VII. 2000, M. M. Yang [楊曼妙] et al. leg., Malaise trap, voucher: NMNS ENT 4450-1975; 3♂♂, Yunghsing LY3, 14–17. VII. 2000, M. M. Yang et al. leg., Malaise trap, voucher: NMNS ENT 4450-1821, 1779, 1787; 1♂, Yunghsing LY4, 14–17. VII. 2000, M. M. Yang et al. leg., Malaise trap, voucher: NMNS ENT 4450-2037; 3♂♂, Yonghsing NO.4,

23. IX. 1998, H. T. Shih & C. H. Chang leg., Malaise trap, voucher: NMNS ENT 3209-1719, 1756, 1765; 1♀, Datianchih [大天池], 10. X. 1998, H. T. Shih leg., Malaise trap, sample ID: 19981010LT2MAHYM003, voucher: NMNS ENT 3209-0133; 1♂, Yunghsing Farm [永興農場] LY3, 14–17. VII. 2000, M. M. Yang leg., Malaise trap, voucher: NMNS ENT 4450-1787; 1♂, Yunghsing Farm LY4, 14–17. VII. 2000, M. M. Yang leg., Malaise trap, voucher: NMNS ENT 4450-2041; 1♂, 13–18. IV. 1981, K.S. Lin, L.Y. Chou, T. Lin, S.C. Lin leg., sample ID: Ichn07081001, det: *Lissopimpla basalis* by H. Townes, 1983, voucher: TARI; 5♂♂, 4–9. V. 1982, K.S. Lin, K.C. Chou, S.C. Lin, C.C. Pan leg., voucher: TARI; 1♂, “Formosa, Kotosho [= present Lanyu island]”, III–IV. 1932, S. Hirayama leg., voucher: TARI; 1♀, “Koutousyo, FORMOSA [= present Lanyu island]”, XII. 1931–II. 1932, S. Hirayama leg., det: *Echthromorpha* sp. by S.C. Chiu, voucher: TARI.

Chinese vernacular name. The Chinese vernacular name is proposed here for the first time. “黑基” (black base) is derived from the specific name “*basalis*,” meaning “basal,” which likely refers to the black coloration of the metasomal T1 in this species.

Distribution. Indonesia (Sumatra, type locality; Java) (Vollenhoven, 1879; Tosquinet, 1903); Philippine (Mindanao, Palawan) (Momoi, 1971); Vietnam (Pham, 2011); Taiwan (Lanyu, new record).

Remarks. This is the first record of this genus from Lanyu island, Taiwan. This finding also extends the known northernmost distribution of this genus.

Figure 1. The Lanyu specimens of *Leptophion vechti* Gaudl & Mitchell, 1981. A. Female lateral habitus; B. Head in anterior view; C. Head in dorsal view; D. Mesosoma in dorsal view, the white triangle indicates the lateral carina of scutellum; E. Mesosoma and head in lateral view; F. Wings with wing vein terminology of Broad et al. (2018) labeled, the black triangle indicates the vestigial ramulus and the gray triangle indicates the proximal corner of hind wing marginal cell; G. Distal hamuli; H. Hind tarsal claw. A–E, G–H: CHP00726; F: CHP00728. Photographed by Hsuan-Pu Chen.

Figure 2. The Lanyu specimens of *Lissopimpla basalis* (Vollenhoven, 1879). A. Female dorsal habitus; B. Female lateral habitus, with zoomed-in view of fore wing M&RS and 1cu-a; C. Female head in anterior view; D. Male dorsal habitus; E. Male lateral habitus, with zoomed-in view of fore wing areolet; F. Male head in anterior view; G. Female mesosoma in dorsal view; H. Female mesosoma in lateral view, the white triangle indicates the median transverse groove on mesopleuron. A–C, G–H: NMNS ENT 3209-133; D–F: NMNS ENT 4450-2041. Photographed by Hsuan-Pu Chen.

Figure 3. The live photos of the newly recorded Darwin wasps from Lanyu island. A. Live *Leptophion vechti* Gauld & Mitchell, 1981 (photographed at 08. V. 2021); B. A group of *L. vechti* gathering and resting on the underside of leaves (photographed at 08. V. 2021); C. Live *Lissopimpla basalis* (Vollenhoven, 1879) (photographed at 11. VI. 2021). Photographed by Cheng-Han Ma.

Discussion

The majority of species in the genus *Leptophion* are restricted to the Indo-Australian region, particularly in Papua New Guinea, Australia, and Indonesia (Gauld & Mitchell, 1981). Although its distribution extends northward into the Palearctic region (Japan), as reported by Shimizu & Watanabe (2015a) with the description of two species, *L. parvus* Shimizu & Watanabe, 2015 and *L. septentrionis*, Shimizu & Watanabe, 2015, their occurrence is limited to the southern boundary of the Palearctic region (Amamioshima island and Yakushima island). Some species, such as *L. radiatus* and *L. maculipennis*, are widely distributed across the Oriental and Indo-Australian regions (Gauld & Mitchell, 1981; Shimizu & Watanabe, 2015b). Given the limited investigation of Ophioninae in Southeast Asia, species currently known from single localities may in fact have broader distributions. Therefore, the discovery of *L. vechti* in Lanyu island suggests it may be present in other areas of Southeast Asia, particularly in regions between Sumatra and Lanyu.

The genus *Lissopimpla* shares a similar distribution pattern with the genus *Leptophion*, with the majority of species known only from the Australasian region (Gauld, 1984; Yu et al., 2016). *Li. albopicta* (Walker, 1860) and *Li. basalis* are the only two species reported from the Oriental region (Yu et al., 2016). The new record of *Li. basalis* from Lanyu island not only extends the

northern boundary of the known distribution of this genus but also suggests the possible presence of this species in intermediate areas of Southeast Asia.

The discovery of two newly recorded species from Lanyu island, both previously known from Southeast Asia, further supports the island's unique biogeographical characteristics. Specifically, it reinforces the hypothesis first proposed by Kano (1933, 1936a, 1936b, 1941) that the biota of Lanyu is more closely related to that of the Philippines than to the geographically closer Taiwan. This study represents the first case supporting Kano's hypothesis based on Darwin wasps. Further investigations of Darwin wasps from Lanyu island are essential for a more comprehensive understanding of the island's distinctive fauna.

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兩種姬蜂（膜翅目：姬蜂科：瘦姬蜂亞科、瘤姬蜂亞科）於蘭嶼之新紀錄向北擴展其分佈範圍

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摘要：本文報導了兩種姬蜂於蘭嶼的新紀錄，分別為威赫特細瘦姬蜂 (*Leptophion vechti* Gauld & Mitchell, 1981) 和黑基麗瘤姬蜂 (*Lissopimpla basalis* (Vollenhoven, 1879))，將其分布範圍向北擴展至蘭嶼。同時，這也是麗瘤姬蜂屬 (*Lissopimpla* Krichbaumer) 的最北分布新紀錄。本文提供了威赫特細瘦姬蜂的重新描述，並修訂了臺灣產細瘦姬蜂屬的檢索表。

關鍵字：檢索表、細瘦姬蜂屬、麗瘤姬蜂屬、生物地理學、動物相研究